

PULSED Nd-YAG LASER WELDING OF A SiC PARTICULATE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOY COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the laser welding behaviour of a SiC particulate reinforced Al-alloy 2124 composite using a pulsed Nd-YAG laser. In that the influences of laser welding parameters of laser intensity, pulse duration and the beam's focus position on the depth of weld penetration as well as the size of fusion zone were investigated. These investigations have led to an optimum welding condition proposed for laser welding of SiC particulate reinforced aluminium alloy composites with minimum defects.

INTRODUCTION

What is very evident is that so little research has been done into fusion welding of metal matrix composite (MMC) materials, especially using lasers, and that much more work is required.

Conventional fusion processes present new challenges when joining MMC materials because most aluminium-based MMCs exhibit high viscosity in the molten state, this in fact causes the composite not to be readily mixed with the filler metal. Another concern is the rejection of the reinforcement phase(s) by the solidification front. Furthermore, most of the matrix/reinforcement systems are not thermodynamically stable, therefore, any joining process that involves high heat input will inevitably upset the existing metastable micro-environment. For instance, prolong exposure of Al-based/SiC composites at reasonably high temperatures may promote reactions between the matrix and the reinforcement phase, in that the formation of brittle Al-carbide phases would cause the corrosion resistance and the toughness of the material to be reduced to an unacceptably low level.

The few welding techniques: gas tungsten arc welding, gas metal arc welding and electron beam welding which have been explored for joining of MMCs were found to be unsatisfactory mainly due to the above mentioned pitfalls [1,2]. Nonetheless, limited success has been achieved in using CO₂ lasers to weld certain types of Al-Si/SiC MMCs [3,4]. The merits of laser welding are apparent: the intrinsic focusing ability and the capability of having precise control over the laser processing parameters are the necessary ingredients contribute for not to cause excessive

damage to the parent microstructure. In addition, the possibility of performing welding without resorting to filler metals is another distinct advantage over many conventional welding techniques. The objective of this study is to establish the laser welding behaviour of Al-based/SiC particulate composites using a pulsed Nd-YAG laser.

EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

Laser welding was accomplished using a JK MS830LD Nd-YAG laser which is capable of operating at a maximum average output power of 120 W. The focal length of the final lens was 80 mm and a beam expanding telescope with a magnification factor of two was used, with such an arrangement a focal spot diameter of 0.08 mm was achieved. The design of the laser head nozzle permits the flow of pure argon at approximately 3 l/min in a coaxial direction to protect the molten pool from excessive oxidation during welding. The laser output parameters were varied in the experiment with the pulse energy (E) ranging from 2 to 12 J/pulse, the pulse duration (t) from 2 to 10 ms, whilst the pulse frequency (f) was fixed at 8 Hz for all the testings. The welding speed was varied by setting the workpiece to traverse at a speed (v) of 10 to 80 mm/min using a CNC controller. Off-focus welding was achieved by moving the workpiece relative to the focal plane.

The MMC used in this study was an aluminium 2124 alloy reinforced with 25(vol)% SiC particles which has an average size of 3 μm . Specimens of size 25mm x 8mm x 3.5mm were prepared for square butt welding, the surfaces for welding were prepared by fine grinding on 600 grit size emery paper then ultrasonically cleaned. Sections of the weld beads for metallographic examination were obtained using wire-EDM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

WELD PENETRATION DEPTH

The effect of peak power (i.e. E/t) on weld penetration depth is shown in Fig. 1, which clearly shows that the depth of penetration increased as E/t was increased and this was true for the three different pulse durations used in the study. The adverse effect of long pulse duration on penetration depth was attributed to the fact that a higher proportion of heat was conducted laterally into the specimen. In fact for a fixed welding condition, the depth of penetration can be predicted by a threshold intensity model [5,6] and using the formula:

$$z \leq \sqrt{\frac{2E}{\pi t I} - R^2(0)} / \theta \quad (1)$$

where, $R(0)$ is the radius of the laser beam at the focal plane, θ is the half-angle of the focused laser beam, E and t is the single pulse energy and pulse duration respectively, and I is the laser intensity at the bottom of the weld.

This relationship clearly shows that under the condition of a constant pulse energy, a shorter pulse duration would mean a deeper penetration. However, too high an intensity would produce weld defects such as cracks and porosity and this effect will be discussed in a later section. The influence of beam defocusing on penetration depth was found to be remarkable (Fig. 2). The maximum penetration was achieved when the focal spot was positioned between 0.2 and 0.7mm below the surface of the workpiece. Perhaps this phenomenon can be

explained by using the threshold intensity model [5,6], by which the theoretical keyhole profile was predicted for different laser welding conditions (Fig. 3). The results show that maximum penetration is reached when the laser spot is focused at a distance Z_m inside the specimen (where Z_m is the on-focus penetration depth). However, in practice the maximum depth of penetration will be difficult to achieve, due to the fact that non-steady state condition always exists in laser welding, moreover, the bottle-neck constriction occurs near the entrance of the keyhole will hinder the full penetration of the laser beam.

Figure 1. Peak power vs. weld depth

Figure 2. Effect of beam defocusing on weld depth

Figure 3. Theoretical prediction of keyhole profile

Figure 4. Peak power vs. weld width

Figure 5. Effect of defocusing on weld width

WELD BEAD WIDTH

The influence of peak power on the width of the weld bead is presented in Fig. 4 which shows that for a constant power a longer pulse duration would produce a larger weld bead. This was considered simply due to a longer heating time.

The effect of defocusing on the width of the weld bead can be seen in Fig. 5. As is predicted by the theoretical keyhole profile shown in Fig. 3, the on-focus welds would always exhibit the minimum bead width and will increase as the off-focus distance increased. In fact, the theoretical model also allows the prediction of the off-focus position at which the maximum bead diameter occurs.

MICROSTRUCTURE OF LASER WELDED MMC

A typical microstructure of a weld section which shown in Fig. 6 reveals that three distinct zones are present, namely: the central weld zone "A", the fusion region "B" and the undisturbed zone "C". Within zone "A", a duplex structure of needlelike precipitates encompassed by somewhat finer and lighter colour platelets were observed. Within region "B", apparently more particles are present as compared to the undisturbed region "C" where the unambiguous banding characteristic of the original material has been preserved. Preliminary results of EDX analysis suggested that the needlelike precipitates and the finer platelets phase appeared in zone "A" correspond to Al_4C_3 and Si respectively; while the particles in zone "B" remain primarily to be SiC, however, EDX analysis also indicated that depending on the welding condition an increase of 6% to 9%(wt.) of SiC particles was detected in this zone as compared to the condition in zone "C".

Figure 6. Typical microstructure of a laser weld

Phase transformation in laser processed Al base/SiC composites are complex and some investigators have demonstrated the formation of unconventional and non-equilibrium phases, but typically the formation of brittle aluminium-carbon compounds such as Al_4C_3 has been widely reported [2,3], and is obeying the following reaction:

Although it has been suggested that such reaction would proceed if the processing temperature exceeds $730^\circ C$ [7], however, the kinetics of reaction and the morphology of the compound itself would undoubtedly be time dependent. Therefore, not only is the laser peak power should be considered as an influential factor in controlling the formation of aluminium carbides, pulse duration also affects the extent to which the reaction occurs.

Figure 7. Microstructure of the weld zone: (a) $t=4ms$, $I=3.2 \times 10^9 W/m^2$; (b) $t=4ms$, $I=6.4 \times 10^9 W/m^2$

Figure 8. Microstructure of the weld zone: (a) $t=4ms$, $I=9.5 \times 10^9 W/m^2$; (b) $t=8ms$, $I=9.5 \times 10^9 W/m^2$

The exact mechanism for the formation of the condense structure as seen in zone "B", though is still being analyzed, was regarded as a consequence of particles migration promoted by the vapour pressure generated during the formation of keyhole. The idea is that when zone "A" is being vaporised, an over-pressure is developed in the keyhole and this will cause SiC particles to migrate from prior zone "A" to zone "B" which itself is in molten state, and finally the particles will redistribute themselves during re-solidification.

The changes of microstructure in zone "A" as a function of pulse intensities and pulse duration are presented in Figs. 7 and 8 respectively. Both the amount and the size of Al_4C_3 plates in zone "A" increased as laser intensity and/or pulse duration was increased. However, Fig. 7a shows that provided that both the pulse intensity and the pulse duration were low enough, in this case was $3.2 \times 10^9 W/m^2$ and $4ms$ respectively, then the amount of carbides formed would become insignificant. Since the presence of excessive Al_4C_3 compound is deleterious to the properties the MMC [8.9] so the amount and the size of carbides should be kept as small as possible.

THE SIZE OF FUSION ZONE

Though in this study the size of HAZ was not determined, it was considered that the size of fusion zone will serve as an indication to the extent to which the base material was affected. Figs. 9 and 10 respectively show the effect of peak power and beam defocusing on the width of fusion zone, of these Fig. 9 shows that the size of fusion zone increased as the pulse intensity and duration were increased. The results simply reflected that a higher energy input would give rise to a larger processed zone. Whereas, Fig. 10 indicates that to defocus the laser beam in either directions would increase the fusion zone size. This was attributed to the fact that defocusing would always reduce the intensity density of the beam because the irradiated area was enlarged and as a result a higher proportion of energy was used in melting the material and the size of the keyhole would correspondingly become smaller.

Figure 9. Peak power vs. fusion zone(FZ) width Figure 10. Beam defocusing vs. FZ width

DEFECTS IN LASER WELDED MMC

Solidification cracks and porosity were found to be the prominent defects in laser welded Al-2124/SiC composite. Porosity are readily formed in zones "A" and "B" due to the high viscosity nature of the molten composite and for this reason did not allow gaseous bubbles to escape easily. For both cracking and porosity, it was found that high laser intensities and short pulse durations would encourage the formation of both defects. In the case of cracking, a short pulse duration would lead to a high cooling rate in the weld which would encourage cracks to develop. A short solidification time also forbids gaseous bubbles to escape fast enough from the weld pool. Furthermore, it is understood that the tendency to cracking increases as the laser intensity is increased (Figs. 11, 12). Therefore, in order to produce minimum defect in laser welded composite it was found that the Nd-YAG laser should be operated at relatively low laser intensities ($\leq 4.0 \times 10^9$ W/m²) with a somewhat longer pulse duration (8-10 ms) synchronized with a proper transverse speed. Under such a condition the weld formed would be largely free of defects and the amount and the size of carbides present in fusion zone "A" would be relatively small. Fig. 13 shows the microstructure of a section of a weld processed under such a condition.

CONCLUSIONS

Pulsed Nd-YAG laser welding technique was employed to join a SiC particulate reinforced Al-Cu based MMC. In general, the results show that by precisely controlling the laser output parameters it was possible to control the geometry of the laser weld bead. The extent to

which the amount of brittle carbides present in the central weld fusion zone was found primarily governed by the laser intensity as well as the pulse duration, by proper controlling these two parameters it was possible to stop excessive carbides formation which are believed to be harmful to the mechanical properties of the material. Under the condition of a relatively low laser intensity and a relatively long pulse-on time, butt welds with minimum defects were produced.

Figure 11. Microstructure of a laser weld performed using condition of $t=4ms$, $I=6.4 \times 10^9 W/m^2$

Figure 12. Microstructure of a laser weld performed using condition of $t=4ms$, $I=12.8 \times 10^9 W/m^2$

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Figure 13. Microstructure of a laser weld performed using an optimum condition of $t=8ms$, $I=3.2 \times 10^9 W/m^2$

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